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Development of creative industries in the conditions of dissemination of information and communication technologies

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In the transformational processes of the development of creative industries in the context of the spread of information and communication technologies, there is a need to rethink the cultural value of using tools to interact with consumers and organize professional activities in cultural and creative institutions. That is why we are increasingly seeing the evolution of the transfer of space of creative sectors in the digital environment, in accordance with the challenges of time.

It is necessary to clearly understand that in the conditions of fierce competition in the socio-cultural environment an important tool is the collaboration of creative industries with business structures in modern digital content. Thus, today's requirements determine the culture of change in the implementation and promotion of cultural products of creative industries through digital transformations, the development of next-generation digital platforms and the promotion of digital initiatives. All this is directly the key to understanding the current and future audience.

An important point is that the creative industries in the spread of information and communication technologies play a threefold role in the national innovation process. In particular, by definition it is the main source of innovative ideas and the emergence of new goods and services; offers services that can be a resource for innovation activities of other enterprises that belong or do not belong to the creative sector; intensively use new technologies and often require their counterparties to adapt to changes in market demand, the introduction of technological change, thereby creating innovative impulses for technology manufacturers, as determined by the specifics of creative industries. That is why the evolution of the information society, the scale of social networks and interactive digital tools are the possibility of their use in the format of digital communication with consumers of creative industries. In general, modern technologies contribute to the adaptation of creative sectors to the globalization processes of society and implement creative ideas in a slightly different way, and most importantly – contribute to the education and branding of creative Ukraine.

Focusing on digital technologies in the development of creative industries in the spread of information and communication technologies, we note that digital tools and digital platforms provide a wide range of opportunities for people to participate in various cultural and creative performances, projects, cultural and recreational resources visiting virtual museums, shows, festivals, concert programs,

acquaintances with the uniqueness of restaurants and hotels in Ukraine, etc. We believe that the concept of implementation and realization of digital technologies radically modernizes the socio-cultural environment in Ukraine and the world in general.

It is worth noting that the effective period of using digital technologies in the creative industries began in 2015. At this time, Ukraine became a participant in the Creative Ukraine program. The program is aimed at supporting cultural and humanitarian projects and provides opportunities for financial support, modernization and investment in the development of the creative sector. At the same time, the activities of the National Bureau of the Creative Europe Program ensure information transparency and openness.

Currently, the principle of digital transformation as a driver of competitiveness is being actively implemented in the activities of creative industries in Ukraine. Digitization is based on the digitalization of social production on the basis of «Industry 4.0», which is implemented through mass distribution in the sectors of creative industries. Thus, in the field of education, digital technologies allow to provide illustrations, virtual additions to educational material; in the field of tourism – to provide virtual guides, transport and logistics of tourist routes, virtual advertising and travel organization, virtual guides, virtual demonstration of services and IT advertising materials. Digital technologies are radically changing the gaming and show business, including offering virtual games with the effect of the presence of a participant in the game. Digital technologies radically modify the entire field of retail, advertising and printing, management and marketing, as well as provide opportunities to obtain objective data on changes in market conditions in real-time.

In accordance with the challenges of the time and with the support of the Ministry of Culture and Information Policy of Ukraine, the Ukrainian Cultural Foundation, the Ukrainian Institute under the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Ukraine, the State Agency of Ukraine for Cinematography, the Ukrainian Book Institute, the Oleksandr Dovzhenko National Center, the Ministry of Digital Transformation and Creative Europe creative industries of Ukraine is gaining significant scale and is becoming an important condition for activity. Digital transformations, wide possibilities of digital space, implementation of the spectrum of virtual and augmented reality, three-dimensional animation, introduction of interactive technologies and systems promote active development of creative industries, ensure competitiveness and create demand for Ukrainian products internationally. After all, the search for new ideas and new meanings will enable the development of creative industries in the context of the spread of information and communication technologies both in Ukraine and internationally.

Analysis of theoretical and practical developments suggests that the culture of change in the creative industries contributes to the activation of digital culture, which penetrates into the ways of communication between art and

audience, and, in fact, in the way of creating cultural and artistic works. Among the key and effective means of digitalization we can single out such digital tools as: cloud technologies; augmented reality element Quick response code technology (QR code); digital mechanism for the exchange of «valuable» data blockchain technology; Scrum-Technology project management tool; 3D sculpting technology; YouTube channel, Facebook, Instagram pages, Telegram channel, podcasts, Instagram Live page, Web sites; ZOOM platforms, Meet; mobile applications Asana, AppStore, Google Play Market, Amazon, Appstore, Opera, Mobile Store; a program in which you can create competitive Quik video content for free; effective communication tools Bring your own device, BYOD, Near Field Communication, NFC; laboratory for finding digital solutions for cultural projects GogolFest_LSD, etc. Thus, the collaboration of digital technologies and cultural products in the space of creative industries contributes to innovative development for the stable and dynamic prosperity of Ukrainian culture.

Thus, in the active process of development of creative industries in the spread of information and communication technologies it is important to develop an algorithm of digital interaction: personality – idea – business – state – management aspect – cultural project – digital technologies – creative industries – civil society. It reflects the slogan «Ukraine of the future is a creative country». It will also help create conditions for artists and representatives of the creative sectors that create a cultural and creative product for promotion in the international space. It is important to realize that right now we have the opportunity to make a change in the information space of understanding the world of Ukraine.

REFERENCES

1. Tsyfrovi instrumenty, yaki dopomozhut khudozhnykam i kulturnym diiacham pid chas karantynu: dobirka. [Digital tools to help artists and cultural figures during quarantine: a selection.]. Ofitsiynyi sait Asotsiatsii «Kultura i kreatyvnist». Retrieved from <https://www.culturepartnership.eu/ua/article/digital-instruments>.
2. Marta Massi, Marilena Vecco and Yi Lin. Digital Transformation in the Cultural and Creative Industries: Production, Consumption and Entrepreneurship in the Digital and Sharing Economy. Taylor&Francis Ltd. 2020. 276 p.
3. Vasina A. et al. Implementation of Digital Technologies into Projects in Area of Creative Industries. In: Ecological-Socio-Economic Systems: Models of Competition and Cooperation (ESES 2019). Atlantis Press, 2020. 26-32.